

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN TRADE IN ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The article discusses the role of foreign trade in international economic relations. The importance of foreign trade in inter-country economic relations has been widely interpreted. Also, information on the effects of foreign trade on the economy, GDP and economic growth of the countries was given. Along with the positive effects of foreign trade on inter-country economic relations, negative effects are explained in detail. Thus, extensive information was given about the crises that occurred in different years and their effects on foreign trade. Also, information was provided on the sanctions applied in the regulation of foreign trade operations. Along with economic sanctions, trade sanctions are also broadly interpreted here. Trade sanctions, such as embargoes, non-tariff barriers, import and export controls, and tariffs and quotas, are discussed extensively. In general, the benefits of foreign trade to the economy of countries have been explained.

Keywords: foreign trade, economic growth, crises, sanctions, import, export.

Foreign trade is the oldest and most important part of foreign economic relations. Foreign trade consists of imports and exports. After the Second World War, foreign trade began to show its influence on the economic development of countries. Also, the development of trade is one of the most dynamic elements of this development, being the basis of the development of the world economy. At present, foreign trade plays an important role in international economic relations by influencing the economic growth of countries [5].

IMPACT OF THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS ON ITALIAN FOREIGN TRADE RELATIONS:

The global financial crisis that occurred in different years has also had its effect on the Italian economy. One of these crises happened in 2007-2009. The impact of the financial crisis that began in 2007 on the real world economy ended in 2010. Italy's economy also appeared to be out of recession, with GDP growing by 1.7% in 2010 [7]. However in 2009, economic activity fell sharply.

From this point of view, Italy has suffered from the crisis even more than other European economies. Also, Italy, on the other hand, limited the direct impact of the crisis through its banks, which proved to be more liquid and solvent than elsewhere in Europe [13].

Nowadays, Italy has successful foreign trade relations with other countries of the world. Regarding Italy's foreign trade relations in today, it should be noted that in November 2022, exports to non-EU-27 countries increased by 22.5% and imports by 26.8% compared to the same month of the previous year [12].

IMPACT OF FINANCIAL CRISES ON FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS:

At the stage of globalization, the economies of the world countries are rapidly integrated. If we look at the national economies of the countries, this integration also shows its influence on the countries' foreign trade.

Thus, during the last 20 years, an increase in the countries' foreign trade has been observed. Developing Countries (LDCs) have made efforts to increase their share of trade transactions. So, these countries are trying to increase their share in exports by applying trade policy. The reason is that the existing foreign exchange reserves are of great importance for the EEC as well as for the economic growth of these countries. The role of foreign trade operations in increasing the volume of foreign exchange reserves is great. If we look at the research conducted on foreign trade, we should note that according to some, the economic growth of countries is supported by export operations, and according to others, the economic growth of countries is supported by import operations [9].

If we look at the Developed Countries (DEC), we should note that in the successful implementation of foreign economic policy in these countries, special attention is paid to creating access to new markets for the sale of local products. Thus, countries expand their economies by developing their foreign trade.

Although foreign trade plays a positive role in inter-country economic relations, the crises that occurred in different years have had a negative effect on inter-country economic relations. As an example of these crises, the crises that occurred in 1929-1933, 1973, 1994-1995, 1997-1998, 2007-2009 and the crises that occurred in the Suez Canal can be mentioned.

The crisis of 1929-1933 is called the biggest financial crisis in the world. In those years, the weakness of the banking system was one of the factors that triggered the beginning of the financial crisis. In these years, the banking system of the United States has differed significantly, both with the current era and with the banking systems of other countries at that time. In those years, the unified banking system was widespread in the United States. This has led to the bankruptcy of a number of banks. By 1920, there were only 18 commercial

banks in Canada, although there were over 30,000 commercial banks in the United States. Also, banks operating in the United States had 1,281 branches, but banks operating in Canada had 4,676 branches. The financial crisis has also affected unemployment. So, if there were 4.3 million unemployed by 1930, in 1931 this number was 8 million, and in 1932, it reached 12 million, and in the first quarter of 1933, the number of unemployed was 13 million [2].

The next crisis was in 1973. This crisis was related to energy. The oil price regulation system in the United States started in 1970. Until 1973, the price of oil in the United States was regulated by government agencies. The oil price shock in 1973-1974 had a negative impact on crude oil supply. Thus, in the last quarter of the year when the crisis began, the amount of crude oil produced decreased, while at the same time, the price of oil increased compared to previous periods. The cause of the energy crisis was the reduction of the oil production volume of OPEC member countries [1].

Another crisis occurred in 1994-1995. This crisis happened in Mexico. Mexico suffered a financial crisis not only in 1994-1995, but also in 1976, 1982, and 1986. As a result of the financial crisis that occurred in December 1994, the value of the peso (the currency in circulation in many South American countries) fell by 40 percent. The cause of the crisis was the Mexican government's decision to devalue the peso by about 15 percent that year. This meant a devaluation of about 4 pesos for 1 dollar. As a result, the peso's exchange rate plummeted, triggering the financial crisis. Also, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita decreased by 9.2 percent, and unemployment was 2 million. However, the Mexican government managed to recover quickly from the effects of the financial crisis that occurred in 1994-1995 [3].

Also, the privatization of Mexico's banking sector was completed in 1992, and foreign inflows increased significantly. Although Mexican banks owed \$8 billion to foreign banks in 1991, this debt was \$16.5 billion in 1994. In 1995, one of the largest banks in Mexico, Serfin, Invertal, Bitel and other banks were recapitalized and the total amount of capitalization of the banks was 950 million dollars. Also, the average capitalization ratio increased from 6.8 percent to 9.6 percent [4].

One of the world financial crises happened in 1997-1998 and this crisis covered South Asian countries. The main reason for the crisis was the rejection of the fixed exchange rate by the Thai government in 1997. During the crisis, exporters and importers were exposed to exchange rate risk, and therefore, they tried to reduce the risks. For this, they were trying to reduce their business to some extent. As a result, the financial

crisis had a negative impact on foreign trade operations. A financial crisis can permanently affect foreign trade operations through 3 main channels. These include:

1. Income channel – so as demand for local goods falls, so do consumers' incomes. As a result, imports and exports also decrease.

2. The other channel is the replacement influence channel - if the crisis is caused by external factors, then this channel is used. As the relative prices of local goods decrease, consumers try to increase their demand for these goods. At the same time, consumers try to reduce their demand for foreign products, which results in a decrease in exports and imports.

3. The most consequential channel is called the wealth channel. Thus, as the demand of consumers for foreign products decreases, imports also decrease. Thus, the countries' economies are able to export more.

In general, the financial crisis that occurred in 1997-1998 reduced the GDP of world countries by 2 trillion dollars [8].

One of the most important world financial crises is the 2007-2009 financial crisis. The main reason for the beginning of the crisis was the irresponsible behavior of investors in the US real estate market. This crisis had a negative impact on the economy of the United States as well as the CIS and the CIS. The crisis resulted in declines in GDP, which was 4.7 percent, the worst decline since 1930 to 2009, and increased unemployment. The financial crisis, in turn, led to the mortgage crisis. Looking at the mortgage foreclosure rate, we should note that this rate was less than 1 percent as of 2007 [10].

In general, this financial crisis should be divided into 4 main stages. The first phase covers the Anglo-Saxon financial crisis. It was basically an operation initiated to prevent Bear Stearns, one of the largest mortgage banks in the United States, from being affected by the financial crisis. The second phase is the border drawing phase, which involved the rescue of countries in turmoil. The third stage was related to the credit reduction operation. Thus, the implementation of the credit contraction operation has become dangerous for the banking systems of many countries. The last stage is related to filling with emission. The main goal of this stage was to balance the demand by increasing the money supply.

As a result, compared to the European economy, the US economy was able to recover from the effects of this crisis sooner. Also, in addition to the crisis, the GDP per working-age person in developed economies varied between 2007 and 2018. This is shown in the graph below:

Figure 1. GDP per working-age person in developed economies in 2007-2018 [11].

One of the crises that happened is the Suez Canal crisis. Suez Canal was established in 1869 and this canal is of strategic importance. Thus, this channel is an important waterway in the trade between Eastern and Western countries. This channel is the main means of transportation of produced oil to consumer markets. Also, this canal is the main route connecting the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea to the Indian Ocean, and as a result, products are transported from European countries to Asian countries, and from Asian countries to European countries. The Suez Canal is one of the world's most important navigation destinations. Currently, 1/10 of the trade is accounted for by the Suez Canal. Despite all this, the annual income of the Suez Canal does not exceed 5 billion dollars [6].

The Suez Canal crisis occurred in 1956. Thus, it began with the invasion of Egypt by Britain, together with France and Israel, to gain control of the Suez Canal.

Also, sanctions are applied to regulate economic relations between countries. Applied international sanctions are one of the main elements of international relations. Sanctions include coercive measures.

In general, sanctions are economic, diplomatic, etc. can be. Economic sanctions, in turn, consist of unilateral sanctions imposed by one country and multilateral sanctions imposed by a group of countries. Economic sanctions include, for example, sanctions applied by countries related to trade, as well as sanctions applied in the financial field, etc. belongs to. One of the trade sanctions is embargo. An embargo is an international trade restriction that means prohibition, and is economic, environmental, etc. can be.

In addition to embargo, import control and export control are also distinguished among the sanctions applied in trade. Thus, export controls, in turn, control the restrictions applied to exported products or services. These restrictions are imposed against the delivery of

goods to the target countries. Import control controls imported products.

Also, non-tariff barriers are distinguished among trade sanctions. Examples of non-tariff barriers include bans on exports and imports, etc. Also, tariffs and quotas are one of the applied trade sanctions. Thus, tariffs and quotas restrict trade without prohibiting it in full. In this regard, they are mainly used to prevent trade flows.

In general, foreign trade transactions form the basis of economic relations between countries. Each country participates in international trade operations to further expand its economic relations. So, each country sells its products to other countries by bringing them to the world market. As a result of this, they achieve economic growth, as well as an increase in GDP and foreign trade turnover of the countries. Also, countries can successfully invest capital for the implementation of international projects. As a result of this, the economies of the countries are further developing and the opportunities to enter the international arenas are expanding.

CONCLUSION

In general, the global financial crises that occurred in the world led to the weakening of the foreign trade relations of the countries of the world, the weakening of the economies of the countries, the decrease of the economic growth, and the decrease of the volume of exports. Nowadays, countries are successfully conducting foreign trade relations with each other by expanding their trade relations. The expansion of foreign trade relations has a positive effect on the economy of countries. In conclusion, we can note that in the future, with the further development of economic relations, the volume of GDP will increase even more.

References

1. Baumeister, C., Kilian, L., Forty Years of Oil Price Fluctuations: Why the Price of oil May Still Surprise Us. – *Journal of Economic Perspectives* – Volume 30, Number 1. – , 2016, 139-160 p.
2. Eigner, P., Umlauf, T.S., The Great Depression(s) of 1929-1933 and 2007-2009? Parallels, Differences and Policy Lessons. – , 2015, 53 p.
3. Feridun, M., AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE MEXICAN PESO CRISIS OF 1994-1995. – *Dogus University Journal*. – , 2007, 28-35 p.
4. Hoyos, M.L., Mexico Peso Crisis (1994-1995): PROCAPTE. – Yale School of Management, Yale Program on Financial Stability Case Study. – *Journal of Financial Crises* – Volume 3, Issue 3. – , 2021, 474-497 p.
5. Jeníček, V., Krepl, V., The role of foreign trade and its effects. – Article. – *University of Economics, Prague*. – , 2009, 211-220 p.
6. Kenawy, Dr.E., The Economic Impacts of the New Suez Canal. – *IEMed. Mediterranean Yearbook*. – *Strategic Sectors | Economy & Territory*. – , 2016, 282-288 p.
7. Luiss Guido Carli., LA POLITICA ECONOMICA ITALIANA NELLA GESTIONE DELLE CRISI: DALLA SPAGNOLA ALLE CRISI DEL SECONDO DOPOGUERRA, 2020/2021, 43p.
8. Ma, Z., Cheng, L.K., The Effects of Financial Crises on International Trade. – , 2005, 253-285 p.
9. Öztürk, E., Özel, H.A., EFFECT OF FOREIGN TRADE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN E-7 COUNTRIES. – *Suleyman Demirel University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*. – , 2018, 358-369 p.
10. Schoen, E.J., The 2007-2009 Financial Crisis: An Erosion of Ethics: A Case Study. – Article. – , 2016, 806-830 p.
11. <https://www.euromonitor.com/article/the-recovery-from-the-global-financial-crisis-of-2008-missing-in-action>
12. <https://www.istat.it/en/archivio/279189>
13. https://www.treccani.it/enciclopedia/l-economia-italiana-di-fronte-alla-crisi_res-d238e0ed-fe7f-11e1-b986-d5ce3506d72e_%28Atlante-Geopolitico%29/